

NEMECYS

NEW MEDICAL CYBERSECURITY AND DESIGN SOLUTIONS

Secure IoT Service Mesh and Connector

SISMc

Contents

1. Icekube, a mini version of the NEMECYS Platform: Release 3.2	5
1.1. Changes in this release	5
1.2. Requirements.....	5
1.2.1. Tailscale	5
1.3. Software	6
1.4. Run Icekube	7
1.4.1. Summary of installation steps	7
1.4.2. To run Icekube	7
1.5. Tips	18
2. SISMc Instructions.....	19
Config-Files.....	19
create config files for Cluster1(Hospital) and Cluster2(Patient)	19
Test to check deployments are working.....	22
Download Istio	23
Create Certs	23
Labels and Secrets	24
Mutual trust across all clusters.....	26
Get secrets.....	28
Get labels	28
Useful commands if labels are wrong	28
MetalLB.....	29
Install MetalLB.....	29
Install Istio	30
Install Istio with Helm	30
Install istiod.....	31
Install Istio eastwestgateway	32
Expose services and Secrets	33
Demo test app.....	34
App Namespace configuration	34
Deploy Application Hello.....	35
Deploy Service	36
Deploy Sleep on raspberry	37
Deploy Sleep Normal	38
DestinationRule and VirtualService	39

Get all	41
Delete	42
Kiali Grafana Propetheus	43
Issues Found	49
Upgrade Raspberry Pi 5	50
App compatibility with arm64 (or multiarch)	50

Table of Figures

Figure 1: iface	6
Figure 2: ifconfig	8
Figure 3: IceKube1	8
Figure 4: IceKube2 certManager	10
Figure 5: IceKube3 Rancher	10
Figure 6: IceKube4 RancherUI	11
Figure 7: IceKube5 Catalogs	12
Figure 8: IceKube6 Apps	13
Figure 9: IceKube8 AppsOptions	14
Figure 10: IceKube7 AppsUpgrade	14

Disclaimer

The NEMECYS project is co-funded by the European Union under grant agreement ID 101094323, by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee grant numbers 10065802, 10050933 and 10061304, and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

The information and views set out in this publication are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, HADEA, UKRI or SERI. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

1. Icekube, a mini version of the NEMECYS Platform: Release 3.2

This is a tool to install a mini version of NEMECYS Kubernetes Platform, a single node cluster.

1.1. Changes in this release

- Rancher URL set to a sslip domain based on the node ip
- Ingress self-signed certificate is now creating using cert-manager and domain has been set to wildcard sslip domain based on the node ip, i.e.
*.\$nodeip.platform.nemecys.sslip.io using nodeip with '-' instead of '.' i.e. 192-168-5-5 vs 192.168.20.220

HTTP Support

- Nginx Server as external Load Balancer
- Removed k3s traefik load balancer
- Pre-requisite checks (i.e. os version)
- Removed command line checks: icekube is now installed with auto checks
- Configuration file to install or re-install specific components

1.2. Requirements

Provision a Linux VM (Ubuntu 18.04 or 20.04) Resources:

Kubernetes Node

- Minimum: 2 cpu cores, 4 GB RAM and 10 GB disk capacity.
- Recommended: 4 cpu cores, 8 GB RAM and 50 GB disk capacity.

These numbers may change since several NEMECYS components will be deployed, check specific requirements for specific components.

1.2.1. Tailscale

Tailscale used as VPN to assign an IP for connectivity between different Locations.

On Raspberry Pi, Laptop VM, and any other client:

Figure 1 Tailscale

Installation

```
curl -fsSL https://tailscale.com/install.sh | sh
sudo tailscale up --ssh
```

Follow the login URL > sign in with GitHub/Google.

Each device now has a stable Tailscale IP (100.x.y.z) and a MagicDNS name like pi.tailnetname.ts.net.

```
tempadmin@A2:~ $ sudo tailscale up --ssh
To authenticate, visit:
https://login.tailscale.com/a/1c
```

In the terminal will show success

```
tempadmin@A2:~ $ sudo tailscale up --ssh
To authenticate, visit:
https://login.tailscale.com/a/1c
Success.
```

1.3. Software

Icekube installs these software utilities and specifically tested compatible versions:

- Docker
- K3s (Kubernetes)

- Helm
- Cert-manager
- Rancher
- Creates a self-signed certificate to use by the ingress controller
- Nginx Ingress Controller
- nginx docker (load balancer)

Once this is set up, the NEMECYS app catalog containing Helm Charts (this has not been defined yet) can be registered and apps can be deployed to icekube.

1.4. Run Icekube

1.4.1. Summary of installation steps

1. Clone the repo or copy from resources to VM
2. Deploy icekube
 - Run the command `icekube.sh nodeip iface` as per instructions. This deploys the Kubernetes platform
 - nodeip: the ip of the node
 - iface: the network interface of the node ip
3. Access Rancher at `https://rancher.$nodeip.platform.nemecys.sslip.io` where `$nodeip` uses '-' instead of '.'
4. Register the catalog(s)
5. If http access is needed, run `patch_nginx.sh`
6. Deploy nemecys components from the Rancher UI
 - Any script required before deploying any component should be in the `icekube/Components` folder
 - Upon deployment of first component import the self-signed certificate in the trusted CA's store

1.4.2. To run Icekube

- Clone the repository or Copy folder icekube (located in the resources folder) to the VM
- Navigate to icekube folder

```
cd icekube
```

- Change permissions

```
chmod +x ./icekube3.2.sh sed -i -e 's/\r$//' ./icekube3.2.sh chmod +x ./patch_nginx.sh sed -i -e 's/\r$//' ./patch_nginx.sh cd ..
```

- Copy icekube to root

```
sudo cp -r icekube/ /root/  
sudo -i cd icekube/
```

- Get iface

```
# Option 1 cat  
/etc/network/interfaces
```

```
# Internal Network Interface  
auto eth0  
iface eth0 inet static  
    address 192.168.20.100  
    netmask 255.255.255.0  
    network 192.168.20.1  
    dns-nameservers 192.168.20.100  
  
# Internet Network Interface  
auto eth1  
iface eth1 inet dhcp
```

Figure 2: iface

```
# Option 1  
# If ifconfig is not installed  
sudo apt-get install net-tools  
  
# run  
ifconfig
```

```
eth0: flags=4163<UP,BROADCAST,RUNNING,MULTICAST> mtu 1500  
    inet 192.168.20.100 netmask 255.255.255.0 broadcast 192.168.20.255  
    inet6 fe80::215:5dff:fed3:9cb prefixlen 64 scopeid 0x20<link>  
    ether 00:15:5d:d3:09:cb txqueuelen 1000 (Ethernet)  
    RX packets 22946 bytes 17333606 (17.3 MB)  
    RX errors 0 dropped 0 overruns 0 frame 0  
    TX packets 40022 bytes 4592068 (4.5 MB)  
    TX errors 0 dropped 0 overruns 0 carrier 0 collisions 0  
  
eth1: flags=4163<UP,BROADCAST,RUNNING,MULTICAST> mtu 1500  
    inet 172.31.57.29 netmask 255.255.240.0 broadcast 172.31.63.255  
    inet6 fe80::215:5dff:fed3:9cc prefixlen 64 scopeid 0x20<link>  
    ether 00:15:5d:d3:09:cc txqueuelen 1000 (Ethernet)  
    RX packets 1459 bytes 601484 (601.4 KB)  
    RX errors 0 dropped 0 overruns 0 frame 0  
    TX packets 1661 bytes 142503 (142.5 KB)  
    TX errors 0 dropped 0 overruns 0 carrier 0 collisions 0  
  
lo: flags=73<UP,LOOPBACK,RUNNING> mtu 65536
```

Figure 3: ifconfig

Run script: where ip is the ip of the vm where k3s will be installed and iface is the network interface of the nodeip for instance `./icekube3.2.sh 192.168.20.220 eth0`

```
# Usage
./icekube.sh ip iface #
i.e:
./icekube3.2.sh 192.168.20.220 eth0
```


Figure 4: IceKube1

Background process

- 1- First, icekube installs Docker
- 2- Then, k3s is installed. Once installed, the installation process will wait and check for K3s to be up and running.
- 3- Helm is installed together with K3s and kubectl.
- 4- Next is to deploy cert-manager in the cluster to provide a ssl certificate for Rancher. The process will wait and check that the cert-manager is running.

Figure 5: IceKube2 certManager

- 5- Then Rancher is deployed in the cluster. The process will wait and check that Rancher is running.

- 6- Next is to deploy the nginx ingress controller. Before this, a self-signed ssl certificate is created using certmanager. Notice that the domain that is configured in the certificate is the one to be used as domain for the components when deployed to icekube which defaults to *.`$nodeip.platform.nemecys.sslip.io`
- 7- IceKube is now ready.

Figure 6: IceKube3 Rancher

- Access Rancher by accessing the Rancher url in the browser ([https://rancher.\\$nodeip.platform.nemecys.sslip.io](https://rancher.$nodeip.platform.nemecys.sslip.io))
- Once in the Rancher UI, Set the admin password (Password must be at least 12 characters).
- Untick Allow collection of anonymous statistics to help us improve rancher (Optional)
- Accept the Terms and Conditions.
- Then navigate to the workloads in the system project

```
# i.e:
```

```
https://rancher.192-168-20-220.platform.nemecys.sslip.io
```

Figure 7: IceKube4 RancherUI

- The nginx ingress controller is by default set to only accept https connections and redirect to https. To use http, run the script patch_nginx.sh which will configure nginx ingress controller to accept http (optional).
- 1- Now that the cluster is up and running, configure the NEMECYS catalog. Navigate to the cluster Default project
- 2- select Repositories
- 3- Create Tools-Catalogs and click the Add Catalog Button.
- 4- In the add catalog dialog, enter the name (nemecysapps) and Description
- 5- Url, select Git repository containing Helm chart or cluster template definitions and add the Git Repo URL. If using a private catalog repository, enter GitLab credentials as username and password (Authentication: Create HTTP Basic Auth Secret) or public repository(Authentication: None).

```
# Repository Example  
https://gitlab.com/repo-public/helm-charts.git
```

- 6 Select the Git Branch. The NEMECYS app catalog has not yet been released
- 7 Click on Create
- 8 A new Catalog will appear in the list of Repositories

Figure 8: IceKube Catalogs

Available apps

- 1- To access the available apps, click on **Apps** • 2- Select the Repository from the Drop list
- 3- Select the app to install.
- 4- Click on install. Application chart Information is displayed about the Application is shown on this screen.
- 5- Select the version required from the list.
- 6- Select the Namespace or Create a new Namespace and Name
- 7- customization option if required and click Next
- 8- Application configuration option application configuration options are available if configured.
- 9- Additional deployment options are available
- 10- Install

Figure 9: IceKube Apps

- 1- Available Options like Delete and Upgrade are available
- 2- Application Logs
- 3- Download Options

Figure 10: IceKube AppsOptions

- 1- New Version
- 2- Upgrade
- 3- Select New available version and click Next
- 4- Select Customize Helm
- 5- Configure new values if required.
- 6- Additional deployment options(optional). click Upgrade
- 7- Success
- 8- Example endpoint {VM IP}: {Nodeport}

Figure 11: IceKube7 AppsUpgrade

Manual installation helm install nemecys-app ./v1.1.3-Ingress/ --namespace ice-app --set volumes.type=local

Ingress Option.

- Once deployed an application, it can be accessed using the url in the ingress, for instance the given example, <https://{APP-Fullname}-{Project}.{NODE-IP with dashes}.{INGRESS-DOMAIN}> i.e: <https://nemecys-app-ice-nginx-nemecys.192-168-20220.nemecys.sslip.io/>
- Other Option to access the app URL is through rancher, using the option Apps > Installed Apps > click on the app > Select the type Ingress Name and click on the Path

If using https, when you access the url, the browser will raise an alert regarding the certificate not being trusted since it is self-signed. The certificate must be exported to a file

- 1- Open application
- 2- Click on Not Secure
- 3- Click on Certificate details
- 4- Click on Details Tab
- 5- Export
- 6- Save as type: PKCS #7, single certificate (*.p7c)
- 7 Close Window

Figure 11: IceKube AppsIngress

and then added to the trusted CA. At least one component needs to be deployed to be able to retrieve the certificate from the browser.

- 1- Click on the 3 dots
- 2- Settings
- 3- Privacy and Security
- 4- Security
- 5- Manage certificates
- 6- Manage imported certificates from Windows
- 7- Trusted Root Certification Authorities Tab
- 8- Import> Next

- 9- Browse the cert saved previously.
- 10- Select All Files (.)
- 11- Select the Cert and click Open and click Next
- 12- Place all certificates in the following store: Trusted Root Certification Authorities > Next
- 13- Finish
- 14- Do you want to install this certificate? Yes
- 15- The import was successful and click Close
- 16- Refresh the Open application (Restart chrome session if needed)
- 17- Not Secure does not appear anymore.

Figure 12: IceKube AppImportCerts

Figure 12 SISMc Rancher UI, Cluster controller

Figure 13 SISMc Cluster View Patient

1.5. Tips

Re-install icekube Kubernetes node

Since in this version, icekube can be configured to install specific software, the cluster could be completely removed and re-installed but make sure the same user from the previous installation is used.

Run the commands

```
k3s-killall.sh k3s-uninstall.sh
```

Those commands are part of the k3s installation.

Clone the icekube repo again to have a new version of icekube.

Edit icekube.cfg file in the icekube folder and add the word "docker" and "nginxlb", which should be the only content for that file. Run command

```
echo "docker" > icekube.cfg echo  
"nginxlb" > icekube.cfg
```

Run the icekube script

```
./icekube.sh ip iface
```

This run will detect that there is an existing .kube dir, and will prompt to answer whether the user running the icekube script has permission to write this directory. Since the same user from the previous installation should be used, "y" should be answered to continue with the installation.

NOTE: With this Deployment you can now Install SSDP.

2. SISMc Instructions

Config-Files

create config files for Cluster1(Hospital) and Cluster2(Patient)

```
# AS root user
```

```
sudo -i
```

```
# Cluster1, Cluster2, Raspberry cp
```

```
.kube/config .kube/backup-config
```

```

# Cluster1
  kubectl config rename-context default hospital
  kubectl config set clusters.default.server https://100.113.158.117:6443
nano ~/.kube/config
  cp ~/.kube/config ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
cat ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
# Cluster2
  kubectl config rename-context default house1
  kubectl config set clusters.default.server https://100.123.171.43:6443
nano ~/.kube/config
  cp ~/.kube/config ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml

  cat ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
# Cluster3 Raspberry Pi 5
  kubectl config rename-context default house2
  kubectl config set clusters.default.server https://100.79.51.46:6443
nano ~/.kube/config
  cp ~/.kube/config ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml

# Cluster4 Raspberry Pi 3
  kubectl config rename-context default house3
  kubectl config set clusters.default.server https://100.96.132.72:6443
nano ~/.kube/config
  cp ~/.kube/config ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml

# change cluster name and user  nano
~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml  nano
~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml  nano
~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml  nano
~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml

  nano ~/.kube/config
  apiVersion: v1 clusters: - cluster:      certificate-
authority-data: LS0tLS1CRUdJTiBDRVJUS...  server:
https://192.168.20.166:6443  name: house2 contexts: -
context:
  cluster: house2
user: house2-user
name: house2 current-
context: house2 kind:
Config preferences: {}
users:
- name: house2-user      user:          client-
certificate-data: LS0tLS1CRUdJ....  client-
key-data: LS0tLS1CRUdJ....

```

```

# Exit from root user
exit

# as vagrant user Cluster1
sudo chown -R vagrant ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml

# as vagrant user Cluster2
sudo chown -R vagrant ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml

# as vagrant user Cluster3
sudo chown -R ice ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml

# as vagrant user Cluster4
sudo chown -R ice ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml
# Cluster2, Copy to Hospital
scp -r ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml vagrant@100.113.158.117:/home/vagrant/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml

# Cluster 3, Copy to Hospital
scp -r ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml vagrant@100.113.158.117:/home/vagrant/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml

# Cluster 4, Copy to Hospital
scp -r ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml vagrant@100.113.158.117:/home/vagrant/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml

# Output
To authenticate, visit: https://login.tailscale.com/a/1cdc342a34a3cb

# From Cluster1 - Hospital
ls ~/.kube/
cat ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
cat ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
cat ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml
export
CTX_CLUSTER1=hospital
export CTX_CLUSTER2=house1
export CTX_CLUSTER3=house2
export CTX_CLUSTER4=house3

# Check nodes

```

```
kubectl get nodes -o wide --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl get nodes -o wide --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl get nodes -o wide --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl get nodes -o wide --context=$CTX_CLUSTER4 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Test to check deployments are working

Deployment

```
kubectl create deploy nginx --image nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl create deploy nginx --image nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl create deploy nginx --image nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Service

```
kubectl expose deployment nginx --port 80 --type NodePort --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl expose deployment nginx --port 80 --type NodePort --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl expose deployment nginx --port 80 --type NodePort --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Nodeport

```
kubectl patch svc nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml \
-p '{"spec": {"ports": [{"port": 80, "protocol": "TCP", "targetPort": 80, "nodePort": 30160}], "type": "NodePort"}}'
```

```
kubectl patch svc nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml \
-p '{"spec": {"ports": [{"port": 80, "protocol": "TCP", "targetPort": 80, "nodePort": 30165}], "type": "NodePort"}}'
```

```
kubectl patch svc nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml \
```

```
-p '{"spec": {"ports": [{"port": 80, "protocol": "TCP", "targetPort": 80, "nodePort": 30170}], "type": "NodePort"}}'
```

```
#  
Test
```

```
curl 100.113.158.117:30160  
curl 100.123.171.43:30165 curl  
100.79.51.46:30170
```

```
# Delete if not needed
```

```
kubectl delete deploy nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete deploy nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete deploy nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete svc nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete svc nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete svc nginx --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Download Istio

```
# download istio 1.27.1
```

```
cd ~
```

```
curl -L https://istio.io/downloadIstio | ISTIO_VERSION=1.27.1 sh -  
cd ~/istio-1.27.1 export PATH=$PWD/bin:$PATH
```

```
# Prechecks
```

```
istioctl x precheck
```

```
# Uninstall istioctl uninstall
```

```
-y --purge
```

Create Certs

```
# From Hospital
```

```
cd ~ mkdir
```

```
certs cd
```

```
certs
```

```
sudo apt install make
```

```

# Cluster 1
# cluster1 is from the config file
make -f ~/istio-1.27.1/tools/certs/Makefile.selfsigned.mk hospital-cacerts
# Output ls
hospital root-ca.conf root-cert.csr root-cert.pem root-cert.srl root-key.pem

# Cluster 2
make -f ~/istio-1.27.1/tools/certs/Makefile.selfsigned.mk house1-cacerts
# Output ls
hospital house1 root-ca.conf root-cert.csr root-cert.pem root-cert.srl root-key.pem

# Cluster 3
make -f ~/istio-1.27.1/tools/certs/Makefile.selfsigned.mk house2-cacerts
# Output ls hospital house1 house2 root-ca.conf root-cert.csr root-cert.pem root-cert.srl root-key.pem

# Cluster 4
make -f ~/istio-1.27.1/tools/certs/Makefile.selfsigned.mk house3-cacerts
# Check house2
ls
hospital house1 house2 root-ca.conf root-cert.csr root-cert.pem root-cert.srl root-key.pem
ls house1 ca-cert.pem ca-key.pem cert-chain.pem
root-cert.pem

```

Labels and Secrets

```

# Get node names and replace commands with the name
kubectl get nodes --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml --show-labels
kubectl get nodes --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml --show-labels
kubectl get nodes --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml --show-labels

kubectl get nodes --context=$CTX_CLUSTER4 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml --show-labels

# Cluster1
# inside certs folder
cd ~/certs

```

```

    # If not created
    kubectl create namespace istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
    kubectl --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.
yml label namespace istio-system topology.istio.io/network=network1
    kubectl --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-
kubeconfig.
yml label node "assdp-master1" topology.kubernetes.io/region=region1
    kubectl --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-
kubeconfig.
yml label node "assdp-master1" topology.kubernetes.io/zone=zone1

    kubectl create secret generic cacerts -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml \
        --from-file="hospital/ca-cert.pem" \
        --from-file="hospital/ca-key.pem" \
        --from-file="hospital/root-cert.pem" \
        --from-file="hospital/cert-chain.pem"
#
Cluster2
    kubectl create namespace istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
    kubectl --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-
kubeconfig.yaml label namespace istio-system
topology.istio.io/network=network2

    kubectl --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml label node "assdp-slave1" topology.kubernetes.io/region=region2

    kubectl --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml label node "assdp-slave1" topology.kubernetes.io/zone=zone2

    kubectl create secret generic cacerts -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml \
        --from-file="house1/ca-cert.pem" \
        --from-file="house1/ca-key.pem" \
        --from-file="house1/root-cert.pem" \
        --from-file="house1/cert-chain.pem"

# Cluster3 raspberry 5
# If not created
    kubectl create namespace istio-system --context="$CTX_CLUSTER3" --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml

```

```

    kubectl --context="$CTX_CLUSTER3" --kubeconfig="$HOME/.kube/house2-
kubeco nfig.yaml" label namespace istio-system
topology.istio.io/network=network3
    kubectl --context="$CTX_CLUSTER3" --kubeconfig="$HOME/.kube/house2-
kubeco nfig.yaml" label node "raspberrypi"
topology.kubernetes.io/region=region3
    kubectl --context="$CTX_CLUSTER3" --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-
kubeconfig. yaml label node "raspberrypi" topology.kubernetes.io/zone=zone3

```

```

    kubectl create secret generic cacerts -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUS
TER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml \
    --from-file="house2/ca-cert.pem" \
    --from-file="house2/ca-key.pem" \
    --from-file="house2/root-cert.pem" \
    --from-file="house2/cert-chain.pem"

```

```

# Cluster4 raspberry 3
# If not created

```

```

    kubectl create namespace istio-system --context="$CTX_CLUSTER4" --kubeco
nfig ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml
    kubectl --context="$CTX_CLUSTER4" --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house3-
kubeconfig.
yaml label namespace istio-system topology.istio.io/network=network4
    kubectl --context="$CTX_CLUSTER4" --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house3-
kubeconfig. yaml label node "a2" topology.kubernetes.io/region=region4
    kubectl --context="$CTX_CLUSTER4" --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house3-
kubeconfig. yaml label node "a2" topology.kubernetes.io/zone=zone4

```

```

    kubectl create secret generic cacerts -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUS
TER4 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml \
    --from-file="house3/ca-cert.pem" \
    --from-file="house3/ca-key.pem" \
    --from-file="house3/root-cert.pem" \
    --from-file="house3/cert-chain.pem"

```

Mutual trust across all clusters

```

# mutual trust across all clusters, > New Step (Optional, added)
# Each cluster trusts workloads signed by the root CAs listed in its mesh-caroot-
cert ConfigMap (in the istio-system namespace).

```

```

# Merge root certs

```

```

    cat hospital/root-cert.pem house1/root-cert.pem > mesh-cacerts.pem
# Multiple
    cat hospital/root-cert.pem house1/root-cert.pem house2/root-cert.pem > mesh
-cacerts.pem

```

```

cat hospital/root-cert.pem house1/root-cert.pem > mesh-cacerts.pem

# Then distribute it to every cluster (Multiple): for
CTX in $CTX_CLUSTER1 $CTX_CLUSTER2 $CTX_CLUSTER3; do
kubect1 create configmap mesh-ca-root-cert \
    -n istio-system \
    --from-file=root-cert.pem=mesh-cacerts.pem \
    --context=$CTX --kubeconfig ~/.kube/$CTX-kubeconfig.yaml
done for CTX in $CTX_CLUSTER1 $CTX_CLUSTER2; do    kubect1
create configmap mesh-ca-root-cert \
    -n istio-system \
    --from-file=root-cert.pem=mesh-cacerts.pem \
    --context=$CTX --kubeconfig ~/.kube/$CTX-kubeconfig.yaml
done

# Or Manual
# Apply to both clusters
kubect1 create configmap mesh-ca-root-cert --from-file=root-cert.pem=mesh-c
acerts.pem -n istio-system \
    --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
kubect1 create configmap mesh-ca-root-cert --from-file=root-
cert.pem=mesh-c acerts.pem -n istio-system \
    --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml

# Adding a new house Later (e.g., house4)
cat mesh-cacerts.pem house2/root-cert.pem house3/root-cert.pem > mesh-cacer
ts-updated.pem
#
Reapply
kubect1 create configmap mesh-ca-root-cert \
    -n istio-system --from-file=root-cert.pem=mesh-cacerts-updated.pem \
    --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1
kubect1 create configmap mesh-ca-root-cert \
    -n istio-system --from-file=root-cert.pem=mesh-cacerts-updated.pem \
context=$CTX_CLUSTER4

# or
kubect1 create configmap mesh-ca-root-cert \
    -n istio-system \
    --from-file=root-cert.pem=mesh-cacerts-updated.pem \
    --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 \
    --dry-run=client -o yaml | kubect1 apply -f - --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1

    kubect1 create configmap mesh-ca-root-cert \
    -n istio-system \
    --from-file=root-cert.pem=mesh-cacerts-updated.pem \

```

```
--context=$CTX_CLUSTER4 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml \ --  
dry-run=client -o yaml | kubectl apply -f - --context=$CTX_CLUSTER4 --kub  
econfig ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Verify trust

```
istioctl proxy-config secret deploy/sleep -n patient --context=$CTX_CLUSTER  
2
```

Get secrets

```
kubectl get secret,cm -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfi  
g ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get secret,cm -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfi  
g ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get secret,cm -n istio-system --context="$CTX_CLUSTER3" --kubekon  
fig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get secret,cm -n istio-system --context="$CTX_CLUSTER4" --kubeco  
nfig ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Get labels

```
kubectl get nodes --show-labels --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.k  
ube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get nodes --show-labels --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.k  
ube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get nodes --show-labels --context="$CTX_CLUSTER3" --kubeconfig ~/.  
.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get nodes --show-labels --context="$CTX_CLUSTER4" --kubeconfig ~/.  
.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get ns istio-system --show-labels --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubec  
onfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get ns istio-system --show-labels --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubec  
onfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get ns istio-system --show-labels --context="$CTX_CLUSTER3" --kub  
econfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get ns istio-system --show-labels --context="$CTX_CLUSTER4" --ku  
beconfig ~/.kube/house3-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Useful commands if labels are wrong

```
kubectl label node <nodename> <labelname>--  
--overwrite=true
```

```
kubectl --context=kind-cluster2 label node "cluster2-control-plane" topology.kubernetes.io/region=region2 --overwrite=true
```

```
kubectl --context=kind-cluster2 label node "cluster2-control-plane" topology.kubernetes.io/zone=zone2 --overwrite=true
```

MetalLB

Install MetalLB

#1. Apply MetalLB Manifest in Master cluster

```
kubectl apply -f https://raw.githubusercontent.com/metallb/metallb/main/config/manifests/metallb-native.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Check if MetalLB Pods are Running

```
kubectl get pods -n metallb-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

You should see pods similar to:

NAME	READY	STATUS	RESTARTS	AGE
controller-7bcd9b5f47-8h597	1/1	Running	0	36s
speaker-b6z72	1/1	Running	0	36s

Step 2: Configure MetalLB Address Pool

You need to provide MetalLB with a range of IP addresses that can be assigned to LoadBalancer services.

```
# Create a MetalLB ConfigMap
cd ~      mkdir metallb      cd metallb
cat <<EOF > 01metallb-config.yaml      apiVersion: metallb.io/v1beta1      kind: IPAddressPool      metadata:      name: istio-pool      namespace: metallb-system      spec:      addresses:      - 192.168.20.100-192.168.20.150
---
apiVersion: metallb.io/v1beta1
kind:      L2Advertisement
metadata:      name: istio-adv
namespace:      metallb-system
spec:      ipAddressPools:
- istio-pool
EOF
```

Apply the ConfigMap

```
kubectl apply -f 01metallb-config.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig
~/ .kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get pods,IPAddressPool,L2Advertisement -n metallb-system --context=
$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/ .kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

You do not need to run istiod or a full Istio control plane on the Raspberry Pi.

You only need the Istio data plane (sidecar or ztunnel) to join the service mesh.

Component	Typical CPU	Typical RAM	Notes
istiod	~300–600 Mi CPU	~500–1000 Mi RAM	Needs high availability, not for edge
istio-proxy (sidecar)	~30–100 Mi CPU	~100–200 Mi RAM	OK for Pi 4, heavy for Pi 3
ztunnel (ambient mode)	~20–40 Mi CPU	~60–120 Mi RAM	Much lighter, good for Pi 3 So on Raspberry

Pi 3 (1 GB RAM):

- don't run the control plane (istiod)
- join as a remote workload connected to a central control plane (running in your hospital cluster)

Recommended Architecture for the Setup:

Role	Runs istiod?	Runs sidecar / ztunnel?	Typical device
Hospital (main cluster)	Yes	Yes	VM / Server
House / Pi 4 (optional)	No	(sidecar or ztunnel)	Raspberry Pi 4
Pi 3 or lightweight nodes	No	(ztunnel preferred)	Raspberry Pi 3

Raspberry pi 3 cannot run ztunnel because it requires 1.5 GB ram and it has 1 GB

Install Istio

Install Istio with Helm

must run this once per cluster before installing istiod.

Add Repo

```
helm repo add istio https://istio-release.storage.googleapis.com/charts
helm repo update
```

```
helm install istio-base istio/base -n istio-system --kube-context=$CTX_CL
USTER1 --kubeconfig ~/ .kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
helm install istio-base istio/base -n istio-system --kube-context=$CTX_CL
USTER2 --kubeconfig ~/ .kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
helm install istio-base istio/base --version 1.27.1 -n istio-system --kub
e-context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/ .kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
# Check status
```

```
helm status istio-base -n istio-system --kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kub  
econfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
helm get all istio-base -n istio-system --kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --ku  
beconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get pods,svc,secret -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kub  
econfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
helm status istio-base -n istio-system --kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubec  
onfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
helm get all istio-base -n istio-system --kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubec  
onfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl  
get  
all,ServiceAccount,CustomResourceDefinition,ValidatingWebhookCo  
nfiguration -  
n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubec  
onfig ~/.kube/hous  
e2-  
kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get all,ServiceAccount,CustomResourceDefinition,ValidatingWebhookC  
onfiguration -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubec  
onfig ~/.kube/hos  
pital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get pods,svc,secret -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kub  
econfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl  
get  
ServiceAccount,CustomResourceDefinition,ValidatingWebhookConf  
iguration -n  
istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubec  
onfig ~/.kube/hospit  
al-  
kubeconfig.yaml
```

Install istiod

```
# Get cluster name
```

```
kubectl config view --minify --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubec  
onfig ~/.kube  
/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml -o jsonpath='{.clusters[].name}'
```

```
kubectl config view --minify --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubec  
onfig ~/.kube  
/house1-kubeconfig.yaml -o jsonpath='{.clusters[].name}'
```

```
kubectl config view --minify --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 -o jsonpath='{.clust  
ers[].name}' --kubec  
onfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
# Output
```

```
house2
```

```
# Install istiod
```

```
helm install istiod istio/istiod -n istio-system --set global.meshID=mesh  
1 --set global.multiCluster.clusterName=hospital --set global.network=network
```

```

1 --kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
  helm install istiod istio/istiod -n istio-system --set global.meshID=mesh1
1 --set global.multiCluster.clusterName=house1 --set global.network=network2
--kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
  helm install istiod istio/istiod --version 1.27.1 -n istio-system --set
g loba.meshID=mesh1 --set global.multiCluster.clusterName=house2 --set
global. network=network3 --kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig
~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml

```

```

helm install istiod istio/istiod \
--version 1.27.1 \
-n istio-system \
--set global.meshID=mesh1 \
--set global.multiCluster.clusterName=house2 \
--set global.network=network3 \
--kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 \
--kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml

```

Get pods

```

kubect1 -n istio-system get pods,svc --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig
~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
kubect1 -n istio-system get pods,svc --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig
~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
kubect1 -n istio-system get pods,svc --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig
~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml

```

#

Uninstall

```

helm uninstall istiod -n istio-system --kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kube
config ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
helm uninstall istiod -n istio-system --kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kube
config ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
helm uninstall istiod -n istio-system --kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kube
config ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml

```

Install Istio eastwestgateway

install

```

helm install istio-eastwestgateway istio/gateway -n istio-system --kube-c
ontext=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml --set netw
orkGateway=network1 --set labels."topology\.istio\.io/network"=network1
helm install istio-eastwestgateway istio/gateway -n istio-system --kube-c
ontext=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml --set
networ kGateway=network2 --set labels."topology\.istio\.io/network"=network2
helm install istio-eastwestgateway istio/gateway --version 1.27.1 -n isti
o-system --kube-context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.

```

```
yaml --set networkGateway=network3 --set labels."topology\.istio\.io/network"
=network3
```

```
# Get pods
```

```
kubectl get pods,svc -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig
~/\.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get pods,svc -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig
~/\.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get pods,svc -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig
~/\.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Expose services and Secrets

```
kubectl apply -f ~/istio-1.27.1/samples/multicluster/expose-services.yaml
--context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/\.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl apply -f ~/istio-1.27.1/samples/multicluster/expose-services.yaml
```

```
--context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/\.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl apply -f ~/istio-1.27.1/samples/multicluster/expose-services.yaml --
context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/\.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
# create secret
```

```
cd ~/secrets/
```

```
istioctl create-remote-
```

```
secret --name=hospital -
```

```
-context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 -
```

```
-k kubeconfig
```

```
~/\.kube/hospital-
```

```
kubeconfig.yaml >
```

```
02cluster1-api-
```

```
server.yaml
```

```
istioctl create-remote-secret --name=house1 --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kub
econfig ~/\.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml > 02cluster2-api-server.yaml
```

```
istioctl create-remote-secret --name=house2 --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kub
econfig ~/\.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml > 02cluster3-api-server.yaml
```

```
# Apply Secret from Hospital 1 to Home 1
```

```
kubectl apply -f 02cluster1-api-server.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kub
econfig ~/\.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml # Apply Secret from Hospital 1 to Home
2
```

```
kubectl apply -f 02cluster1-api-server.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kub
econfig ~/\.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
# Apply Secret from Home 1 to Hospital 1
```

```
kubectl apply -f 02cluster2-api-server.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kub
econfig ~/\.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml # Apply Secret from Home 2 to
Hospital 1
```

```
kubectl apply -f 02cluster3-api-server.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kub  
econfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
# Get secrets
```

```
# Secrets in Hospital
```

```
kubectl get secret -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubecofig ~  
/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get secret -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubecofig ~  
/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get secret -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubecofig ~  
/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
# raspberry
```

```
kubectl get secret -n istio-system --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubecofig ~  
/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Demo test app

Master: ASSDP-Master1 /home/vagrant/Apps/test/

App Namespace configuration

```
kubectl create ns test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubecofig ~/.kube/hospi  
tal-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl create ns test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubecofig ~/.kube/house  
1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl create ns test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubecofig ~/.kube/house  
2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl label ns test istio-injection=enabled --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --k  
ubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl label ns test istio-injection=enabled --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --k  
ubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl label ns test istio-injection=enabled --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --k  
ubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
# Get Namespaces
```

```
kubectl get ns test --show-labels --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubecofig ~/  
.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get ns test --show-labels --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubecofig ~/  
.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get ns test --show-labels --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubecofig ~/  
.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Deploy Application Hello

```
cat > 03hello-v1.yaml <<'EOF'
apiVersion: apps/v1 kind:
Deployment metadata:
  name: hospital-v1
labels: app:
hospital version:
v1 spec: replicas:
1 selector:
matchLabels:
app: hospital
version: v1
template:
metadata:
labels: app:
hospital
version: v1 spec:
containers: -
name: hospital
  image: registry.gitlab.com/repo-public/hello-v3:1.0
resources: requests: cpu: "100m"
  imagePullPolicy: IfNotPresent #Always
ports:
  - containerPort: 5000
```

EOF

```
cat > 03hello-v2.yaml
<<'EOF' apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment metadata:
  name: house1-v2
labels:
  app: hospital
version: v2 spec:
  replicas: 1
selector:
matchLabels:
app: hospital
version: v2
template:
metadata:
labels:
  app: hospital
version: v2 spec:
containers: -
name: house1
  image: registry.gitlab.com/repo-public/hello-v3:2.0
resources: requests: cpu: "100m"
```

```
        imagePullPolicy:    IfNotPresent    #Always
ports:
  - containerPort: 5000
```

EOF

```
cat > 03hello-v3.yaml
<<'EOF' apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment metadata:
  name:          house2-v3
labels:
  app: hospital
version: v3 spec:
  replicas: 1
selector:
matchLabels:
app: hospital
version: v3
template:
metadata:
labels:      app:
hospital
version: v3
spec:
containers:  -
name: house2
      image: registry.gitlab.com/repo-public/hello-v4:4.0-multi
resources:   requests:      cpu: "100m"
      imagePullPolicy:    IfNotPresent    #Always
ports:
  - containerPort: 5000
```

EOF

Apply

```
kubectl apply -f 03hello-v1.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeco
nfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl apply -f 03hello-v2.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeco
nfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl apply -f 03hello-v3.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeco
nfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Deploy Service

```
cat <<EOF > 03hello-service.yaml
apiVersion: v1 kind: Service
metadata:
  name:      hospital
labels:     app:
hospital   service:
```

```
hospital      spec:
ports:    - port: 5000
name:      http
selector:
  app: hospital
```

EOF

Apply

```
kubectl apply -f 03hello-service.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --k
ubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl apply -f 03hello-service.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --k
ubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl apply -f 03hello-service.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --k
ubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl get all -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig
~/.kube/house2kubeconfig.yaml
```

Deploy Sleep on raspberry

```
cat > 03request-arm64.yaml <<'EOF'
apiVersion: apps/v1      kind:
Deployment metadata:
  name: request
spec: replicas:
1 selector:
matchLabels:
app: request
template:
metadata:
labels:
  app: request      spec:
terminationGracePeriodSeconds: 0
serviceAccountName: request
containers:
- name: request
image: busybox:stable
  command: ["sh", "-c", "sleep infinity"]
imagePullPolicy: IfNotPresent      volumeMounts:
- mountPath: /etc/sleep/tls
name: secret-volume      volumes:
- name: secret-volume
secret: secretName: sleep-
secret      optional: true
EOF
```

Deploy Sleep Normal

```
cat <<EOF > 03request.yaml
```

```
# Copyright Istio Authors
#
# Licensed under the Apache License, Version 2.0 (the "License"); #
you may not use this file except in compliance with the License.
# You may obtain a copy of the License at #
# http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0
#
# Unless required by applicable law or agreed to in writing, software
# distributed under the License is distributed on an "AS IS" BASIS,
# WITHOUT WARRANTIES OR CONDITIONS OF ANY KIND, either express or implied.
# See the License for the specific language governing permissions and #
limitations under the License.

#####
#####
# Sleep service
#####
#####
apiVersion: v1 kind:
ServiceAccount
metadata:
  name: request
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: request
labels:
  app: request
service: request
spec: ports: -
port: 80 name:
http selector:
  app: request
--- apiVersion:
apps/v1 kind:
Deployment
metadata:
  name: request spec:
  replicas: 1
selector:
matchLabels:
app: request
template:
```

```

metadata:
labels:
  app: request          spec:
terminationGracePeriodSeconds: 0
serviceAccountName: request
containers:
  - name: request
    image: curlimages/curl
command: ["/bin/sleep", "infinity"]
imagePullPolicy: IfNotPresent
volumeMounts:
- mountPath: /etc/sleep/tls
name: secret-volume    volumes:
- name: secret-volume
secret: secretName: sleep-secret
secret optional: true
EOF
#
apply
kubect1 apply -f 03request.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubecon
fig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
kubect1 apply -f 03request.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubecon
fig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml

kubect1 apply -f 03request.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubecon
fig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml

# raspberrry Pi 5
kubect1 apply -f 03request-arm64.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --ku
ubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml

kubect1 delete -f 03request.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubecon
nfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml

```

DestinationRule and VirtualService

Apply virtual Service in all Clusters

```

cat > 04vs-hello.yaml <<'EOF'
apiVersion: networking.istio.io/v1beta1
kind: VirtualService metadata:
  name: vs1-hello
namespace: test
spec:
  hosts:
  - hospital
http:
- route:
- destination:          host: hospital          subset: v1          weight:
  30
- destination:

```

```
        host: hospital
subset: v2
weight: 30      -
destination:
host: hospital
subset: v3
weight: 40
EOF
```

Apply the Configuration

```
kubectl apply -f 04vs-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl apply -f 04vs-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl apply -f 04vs-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Apply destination rule in all clusters

```
cat > 05destinationrule-hello.yaml <<'EOF'
apiVersion: networking.istio.io/v1beta1
kind: DestinationRule metadata:
  name: hospital
namespace: test
spec: host:
  hospital
subsets:      -
name: v1
labels:
version: v1    -
name: v2
labels:
version: v2    -
name: v3
labels:
  version: v3
```

EOF

Apply the Configuration

```
kubectl apply -f 05destinationrule-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl apply -f 05destinationrule-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl apply -f 05destinationrule-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Get all

```
kubectl get all,DestinationRule,VirtualService -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
kubectl get all,DestinationRule,VirtualService -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
# raspberry Pi 5
kubectl get all,DestinationRule,VirtualService -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

Test

```
for i in {1..20}; do
  kubectl exec --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml -n test -c request "$(kubectl get pod --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml -n test -l app=request -o jsonpath='{.items[0].metadata.name}')" -- curl hospital:5000/hello done
  for i in {1..20}; do
    kubectl exec --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml -n test -c request "$(kubectl get pod --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml -n test -l app=request -o jsonpath='{.items[0].metadata.name}')" -- curl hospital:5000/hello done
    for i in {1..20}; do
      kubectl exec --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml -n test -c request "$(kubectl get pod --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml -n test -l app=request -o jsonpath='{.items[0].metadata.name}')" -- curl hospital:5000/hello done
    done
  done

  kubectl exec --context="$CTX_CLUSTER1" --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml -n test -c request "$(kubectl get pod --context="$CTX_CLUSTER1" --kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml -n test -l app=request -o jsonpath='{.items[0].metadata.name}')" -- curl hospital:5000/hello
  kubectl exec --context="$CTX_CLUSTER3" --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml -n test -c request "$(kubectl get pod --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml -n test -l app=request -o jsonpath='{.items[0].metadata.name}')" -- curl hospital:5000/hello
```

View in SISM

Figure 14 SISMc View Secure Connectivity

Delete

```
kubectl delete -f 03hello-service.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 -
kubeconfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete -f 03hello-service.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 -
kubeconfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete -f 03hello-service.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 -
kubeconfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete -f 03hello-v1.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubec
onfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete -f 03hello-v2.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubec
onfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete -f 07hello-v3.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubec
onfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete -f 03sleep.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubec
onfig ~/.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete -f 03sleep.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubec
onfig ~/.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete -f 03sleep.yaml -n test --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubec
onfig ~/.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete -f 04vs-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 --kubeconfig ~/
.kube/hospital-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete -f 04vs-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 --kubeconfig ~/
.kube/house1-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```
kubectl delete -f 04vs-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 --kubeconfig ~/
.kube/house2-kubeconfig.yaml
```

```

    kubectl delete -f 05destinationrule-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER1 -
kubecofig ~/.kube/hospital-kubecofig.yaml
    kubectl delete -f 05destinationrule-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER2 -
kubecofig ~/.kube/house1-kubecofig.yaml
    kubectl delete -f 05destinationrule-hello.yaml --context=$CTX_CLUSTER3 -
kubecofig ~/.kube/house2-kubecofig.yaml

```

Kiali Grafana Propetheus

registry.gitlab.com/repo-public/kiali

```
# add Kiali
```

```

```yaml
cat <<EOF > kiali-nemecys.yaml

Source: kiali-
server/templates/serviceaccount.yaml apiVersion: v1
kind: ServiceAccount metadata: name: kiali
namespace: "istio-system" labels:
helm.sh/chart: kiali-server-2.0.0 app: kiali
 app.kubernetes.io/name: kiali
app.kubernetes.io/instance: kiali
version: "v2.0.0"
 app.kubernetes.io/version: "v2.0.0"
app.kubernetes.io/managed-by: Helm
app.kubernetes.io/part-of: "kiali" ...

Source: kiali-server/templates/configmap.yaml
apiVersion: v1 kind: ConfigMap metadata: name:
kiali namespace: "istio-system" Labels:
 helm.sh/chart: kiali-server-2.0.0
 app: kiali
 app.kubernetes.io/name: kiali
app.kubernetes.io/instance: kiali
version: "v2.0.0"
 app.kubernetes.io/version: "v2.0.0"
app.kubernetes.io/managed-by: Helm
app.kubernetes.io/part-of: "kiali" data:
 config.yaml: |
additional_display_details: -
annotation: kiali.io/api-spec
icon_annotation: kiali.io/api-type
title: API Documentation auth:
 openid: {}
openshift:
client_id_prefix: kiali

```

```

strategy: anonymous
clustering:
autodetect_secrets:
enabled: true
 Label: kialli.io/multiCluster=true
clusters: [] deployment:
 additional_service_yaml: {}
affinity: node: {}
pod: {} pod_anti: {}
cluster_wide_access: true
configmap_annotations: {}
custom_envs: []
custom_secrets: [] dns:
 config: {} policy:
 "" host_aliases: [] hpa:
api_version: autoscaling/v2
spec: {} image_digest: ""
 image_name: registry.gitlab.com/repo-public/kiali
image_pull_policy: Always image_pull_secrets: []
image_version: v2.3 ingress:
 additional_labels: {}
class_name: nginx
override_yaml:
metadata: {}
ingress_enabled: false
instance_name: kialli
logger: log_format:
text log_level: info
sampler_rate: "1"
 time_field_format: 2006-01-02T15:04:05Z07:00
namespace: istio-system
 node_selector: {}
pod_annotations: {} pod_labels:
sidecar.istio.io/inject: "false"
priority_class_name: "" replicas:
1 resources: limits:
 memory: 1Gi
requests: cpu: 10m
memory: 64Mi
secret_name: kialli
security_context: {}
service_annotations: {}
service_type: ""
tolerations: []
version_label: v2.0.0
view_only_mode: false
external_services:

```

```

custom_dashboards:
enabled: true istio:
 root_namespace: istio-system
tracing:
 enabled: false grafana:
url: "http://grafana.istio-system:3000"
ui: branding: title: "NEMECYS
SISMc"
 LoginTitle: "Welcome to ICE's NEMECYS Service Mesh UI"
subtitle: "Powered by Kiali, Integrated by ICE"
primaryColor: '#01404E' secondaryColor: '#16A7E0'
accentColor: '#DA404D'

```

```

identity:
 cert_file: ""
private_key_file: ""
istio_namespace: istio-system
kiali_feature_flags:
disabled_features: []
validations: ignore:
- KIA1301 Login_token:
signing_key: CHANGEME00000000
server: observability:
 metrics:
enabled: true
port: 9090 port:
20001 web_root:
/kiali ...

```

```

Source: kiali-server/templates/role.yaml
apiVersion: rbac.authorization.k8s.io/v1
kind: ClusterRole metadata: name: kiali
labels: helm.sh/chart: kiali-server-
2.0.0
 app: kiali
app.kubernetes.io/name: kiali
app.kubernetes.io/instance: kiali
version: "v2.0.0"
app.kubernetes.io/version: "v2.0.0"
app.kubernetes.io/managed-by: Helm
app.kubernetes.io/part-of: "kiali"
rules: - apiGroups: [""] resources:
- configmaps
- endpoints - pods/log verbs: - get
- list
- watch - apiGroups: [""] resources: - namespaces
- pods
- replicationcontrollers - services verbs: - get

```

```

- list
- watch
- patch - apiGroups: [""] resources: - pods/portforward verbs: - create
- post
- apiGroups: ["extensions", "apps"] resources:
- daemonsets
- deployments
- replicaset - statefulsets verbs: - get
- list
- watch
- patch - apiGroups: ["batch"] resources: - cronjobs - jobs verbs: -
get
- list
- watch
- patch - apiGroups:
- networking.istio.io - security.istio.io
- extensions.istio.io
- telemetry.istio.io - gateway.networking.k8s.io resources: ["*"] verbs:
- get
- list
- watch
- create
- delete
- patch
- apiGroups: ["apps.openshift.io"] resources: - deploymentconfigs verbs:
- get
- list
- watch
- patch
- apiGroups: ["project.openshift.io"] resources: - projects verbs:
- get
- apiGroups: ["route.openshift.io"] resources: - routes verbs:
- get
- apiGroups: ["authentication.k8s.io"] resources: - tokenreviews verbs:
- create
- apiGroups: ["oauth.openshift.io"] resources: - oauthclients
resourceNames: - kiali-istio-system verbs:
- get
- apiGroups: ["admissionregistration.k8s.io"] resources:
- mutatingwebhookconfigurations verbs:
- get
- list - watch ...

Source: kiali-server/templates/rolebinding.yaml
apiVersion: rbac.authorization.k8s.io/v1 kind:
ClusterRoleBinding metadata: name: kiali
Labels: helm.sh/chart: kiali-server-2.0.0
app: kiali app.kubernetes.io/name: kiali

```

```
app.kubernetes.io/instance: kiali version:
"v2.0.0" app.kubernetes.io/version: "v2.0.0"
app.kubernetes.io/managed-by: Helm
app.kubernetes.io/part-of: "kiali" roleRef:
apiGroup: rbac.authorization.k8s.io kind:
ClusterRole name: kiali subjects: - kind:
ServiceAccount name: kiali namespace:
"istio-system" ...
```

---

```
Source: kiali-server/templates/service.yaml
apiVersion: v1 kind: Service metadata: name:
kiali
```

```
namespace: "istio-system" Labels:
helm.sh/chart: kiali-server-2.0.0
app: kiali
app.kubernetes.io/name: kiali
app.kubernetes.io/instance: kiali
version: "v2.0.0"
app.kubernetes.io/version: "v2.0.0"
app.kubernetes.io/managed-by: Helm
app.kubernetes.io/part-of: "kiali"
annotations:
spec: ports: - name: http
appProtocol: http protocol: TCP
port: 20001 - name: http-metrics
appProtocol: http protocol: TCP
port: 9090 selector:
app.kubernetes.io/name: kiali
app.kubernetes.io/instance: kiali
```

...

---

```
Source: kiali-server/templates/deployment.yaml
apiVersion: apps/v1 kind: Deployment metadata:
name: kiali namespace: "istio-system"
Labels: helm.sh/chart: kiali-server-2.0.0
app: kiali app.kubernetes.io/name: kiali
app.kubernetes.io/instance: kiali version:
"v2.0.0" app.kubernetes.io/version:
"v2.0.0" app.kubernetes.io/managed-by: Helm
app.kubernetes.io/part-of: "kiali" spec:
replicas: 1 selector:
matchLabels:
app.kubernetes.io/name: kiali
app.kubernetes.io/instance: kiali
strategy: rollingUpdate:
maxSurge: 1
maxUnavailable: 1 type:
RollingUpdate template: metadata:
```

```

name: kialli Labels:
helm.sh/chart: kialli-server-2.0.0
app: kialli
app.kubernetes.io/name: kialli
app.kubernetes.io/instance: kialli
version: "v2.0.0"
 app.kubernetes.io/version: "v2.0.0" app.kubernetes.io/managed-by:
Helm app.kubernetes.io/part-of: "kialli" sidecar.istio.io/inject:
"false" annotations: checksum/config:
03a677accc379d7d5b7b3c74464dc72867b31f794e5beaa98221 ba19c5735016
prometheus.io/scrape: "true" prometheus.io/port: "9090"
kialli.io/dashboards: go,kialli spec: serviceAccountName: kialli
containers:
- image: "registry.gitlab.com/repo-
 public/kialli:v2.3"
 imagePullPolicy: Always name:
 kialli command:
- "/opt/kialli/kialli"
- "-config"
- "/kialli-configuration/config.yaml"
 securityContext:
 allowPrivilegeEscalation: false
 privileged: false
 readOnlyRootFilesystem: true
 runAsNonRoot: true
 capabilities:
 drop:
- ALL
ports:
- name: api-port containerPort:
 20001 - name: http-metrics
 containerPort: 9090
 readinessProbe: httpGet:
 path: /kialli/healthz port:
 api-port scheme: HTTP
 initialDelaySeconds: 5
 periodSeconds: 30 livenessProbe:
 httpGet: path: /kialli/healthz
 port: api-port scheme: HTTP
 initialDelaySeconds: 5
 periodSeconds: 30 env:
- name: ACTIVE_NAMESPACE
 valueFrom: fieldRef:
 fieldPath: metadata.namespace
- name: LOG_LEVEL value: "info"
- name: LOG_FORMAT value:
 "text" - name:
 LOG_TIME_FIELD_FORMAT value:

```

```

"2006-01-02T15:04:05Z07:00" -
name: LOG_SAMPLER_RATE value:
"1" volumeMounts: - name:
kiali-configuration mountPath:
"/kiali-configuration"
- name: kiali-cert mountPath:
"/kiali-cert" - name: kiali-
secret mountPath: "/kiali-
secret" - name: kiali-cabundle
mountPath: "/kiali-cabundle"
resources: limits:
memory: 1Gi requests:
cpu: 10m memory: 64Mi
volumes:
- name: kiali-configuration
 configMap: name: kiali -
 name: kiali-cert secret:
 secretName: istio.kiali-service-account
optional: true - name: kiali-secret
secret: secretName: kiali
optional: true - name: kiali-cabundle
configMap:
 name: kiali-cabundle
optional: true ...

```

EOF

```

kubectl apply -f kiali-nemecys.yaml
kubectl apply -f ~/istio-1.27.1/samples/addons/prometheus.yaml
kubectl apply -f ~/istio-1.27.1/samples/addons/grafana.yaml #
patch
kubectl get all -n istio-system
kubectl patch svc kiali -n istio-system -p '{"spec": {"ports": [{"name": "http", "port": 20001, "protocol": "TCP", "targetPort": 20001, "nodePort": 31000}], "type": "NodePort"}}'

```

# URL <http://192.168.20.210:31000/kiali/>

## Issues Found

The installed operating system (OS) does not indicate support for Raspberry Pi 5 - Ubuntu 20.04.5 for Raspberry Pi does not have support for Pi 5 hardware. - Option recommended: Use Ubuntu 22.04 or 24.04 arm64 for Pi 5 - Use Raspberry Pi imager to load the custom image and installed it in the microsd

Tested in raspberry 5 <https://cdimage.ubuntu.com/releases/20.04/release/>  
<https://cdimage.ubuntu.com/releases/22.04/release/> ubuntu-24.04.3-preinstalled-serverarm64+raspi.img.xz

## Upgrade Raspberry Pi 5

```
change hostname
sudo hostnamectl set-hostname raspberrypi
Edit the /etc/hosts file: by entering
sudo nano /etc/hosts
Find: the line that starts with 127.0.1.1 and change the old hostname to your
new one.
Save: the file by pressing Ctrl+x, then Y, and then Enter.
Reboot: your Raspberry Pi.
#First boot setup:
sudo apt update && sudo apt upgrade -y uname
-m # expect: aarch64 ok

confirm kernel support Pi 5:
ls /boot/firmware/*rpi-5-b.dtb
App compatibility with arm64 (or multiarch)
error: exec /usr/local/bin/gunicorn: exec
format error

Build a new image with
docker login -u informationcatalyst registry.gitlab.com

docker buildx create --use --name multi || docker buildx use multi
docker buildx build --platform linux/amd64,linux/arm64 -t
registry.gitlab.com/repo-public/hello-v4:4.0-multi --push --provenance=false
--sbom=false .
```